

See discussions, stats, and author profiles for this publication at: <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/367380120>

A Conceptual Framework for Understanding Adoption and Diffusion of Performance-Based Funding in European Higher Education* A Conceptual Framework for Understanding Adoption and Dif...

Conference Paper · June 2020

CITATIONS

0

READS

50

2 authors, including:

Ijaz Ahmad

University of Georgia

6 PUBLICATIONS 91 CITATIONS

SEE PROFILE

A Conceptual Framework for Understanding Adoption and Diffusion of Performance-Based Funding in European Higher Education*

Ijaz Ahmad

University of Georgia

James C. Hearn

University of Georgia

June 2020

*Paper for presentation at the 36th annual Colloquium of the European Group for Organizational Studies, online, July 2020. Please address correspondence to Ijaz Ahmad at Ijaz.Ahmad@uga.edu.

A Conceptual Framework for Understanding Adoption and Diffusion of Performance-Based Funding in European Higher Education

Abstract

There is a reason to question the most commonly stated determinants for the adoption and diffusion of performance-based funding (PBF) model in Europe. While the spread of New Public Management and other movements no doubt are associated enthusiasm for PBF, these movements do not fully explain the phenomenon in the diverse set of European tertiary education systems. Therefore, to address conceptual and methodological limitations in previous studies and to better understand the phenomenon, we intend to conduct a quantitative study which may be guided by a robust conceptual framework. As a stepping-stone, we propose here a conceptual framework for the adoption and diffusion of PBF in European higher education. This framework encompasses most of the institutional, national, and supranational actors and the varied contexts in which these actors coordinate. As a preliminary step to verify our conceptual framework, we performed a descriptive study involving eight variables. Our analysis suggests that while population size and growth rate are not substantial factors in the adoption of accountability policies in European higher education, gross tertiary enrolment, tertiary enrolment rate, and tertiary expenditure (as % of total governmental expenditure on education) seem significant factors in the adoption and diffusion of accountability policies in European higher education. We aim to stimulate a discussion on the topic contributing to enriched understanding and research on the topic.

Introduction

The performance-based funding (PBF) model is part of a broader accountability movement in public higher education across the world (de Boer, 2019; McLendon & Hearn, 2013), where the performance of higher education institutions (HEIs) is measured in terms of 'student retention and graduation rates,' 'undergraduate access,' 'institutional efficiency,' 'job placement rates,' 'faculty productivity,' and so on. Although the state of Tennessee in the United States was a pioneer in adopting the PBF model in 1979-80, at the turn of the 20th century, some half of the states in the US had adopted this model. However, some of the states later abandoned the model due to difficulty in implementation, fiscal and political cost attached to performance measurement, and the uncertain outcome of the model (McLendon & Hearn, 2013, p.25-26). After initial abatement or abandoning of the idea, scholars in the US are witnessing the resurgence of the PBF model with some revisions. In the new system, the focus is on the financing of degree production, developing human capital for the states, efficient alignment of mission, measures, and incentives. In addition to outputs, some intermediate indicators, called throughputs, such as completion of "gateway" courses, are also taken into consideration. Claeys-Kulik and Eastermann (2015) reported that during the last three decades, twelve out of 28 European higher education systems they surveyed had adopted the output-oriented (ex-post) formula funding model (p.39), while ten systems had adopted a performance agreement(ex-ante) model for funding (p.35). In our recent data collection on the adoption of PBF in European higher education systems, we learned that 20 European countries have already adopted the new PBF model. All sixteen German states (länder), the Flemish part of Belgium higher education system, and two constituent countries of the United Kingdom (England and Wales) have also adopted this new funding system.

Kelchen (2018) has indicated that the new forms of accountability measures have come from the New Public Management (NPM) movement, which started in the 1980s. Jongbloed et al. (2018) also argued that PBF has come to higher education through the NPM movement.

Among the other cited determinants of the PBF model are declining public funding, increasing need for accountability (Kivistö & Kohtamäki, 2016; McLendon & Hearn, 2013), improving the quality of higher education (Boer et al., 2015), creating value for money, aligning goals of HEIs with the public policy goals (Frølich, 2008; Kivistö & Kohtamäki, 2016), or sometimes even adopting it only for symbolic purposes with little intention to improve institutional performance (Kivistö & Kohtamäki, 2016).

However, it is surprising that many of these scholars have discussed the determinants of adoption of PBF only at the cursory level. Therefore, what is not clear is how various social, demographic, cultural, political, organizational, and economic factors in European countries shaped their adoption of the PBF model during the last three decades. McLendon *et al.* (2006) challenged the apparent reasons for the adoption and diffusion of the PBF model in the US higher education and quantitatively investigated the broader socio-politico-economic factors to fully explain the cases of adoption as well as late adoption or non-adoption. This approach resonates with the ideas of Huisman and Currie (2004). They argued that the adoption of higher education policies could be explained through geographic and historical contexts, ideological shift, changing relationships between governments and universities, globalization, internationalization of higher education, and developments of informational and communication technologies. Also, the effects of these factors differ across various historical contexts, the way national governments decide to implement accountability mechanisms, and how the governments are approaching globalization as a neo-liberal economic ideology. In other words, the effect of globalization or new liberal ideology, including NPM, is mediated by the state and institutional context. Broucker *et al.* (2016) also pointed out that the governments use NPM as a toolbox, containing many instruments that governments can choose from depending upon a time, focus, and topical policy goals. In sum, NPM may have contributed to the adoption of the PBF model, but in some cases, NPM could itself have been affected by the broader socio-politico-economic factors. These factors must be identified not only for understanding the adoption and diffusion of PBF in the first place but also to assess its impact and to explain the perplexing trend in Europe where some countries are now moving away from PBF, others are still contemplating its adoption and there are some countries who seem indifferent about it.

Kivistö and Kohtamäki (2016) noticed in their review of PBF impact studies, that not only was there a dearth of studies conducted in Europe on the adoption of the PBF model, but also European studies were mainly qualitative. They were "without solid (quantitative) empirical data or systematic analysis" (p.216). They further argued that due to a small number of comprehensive multivariate studies conducted in Europe, generalizability becomes a challenge, primarily because the performance of HEIs depends upon a host of different contextual factors across European systems (p.221). Brennan (2010) also argued that there is a need for both quantitative and qualitative comparative research for a better understanding of the interaction between higher education and society in its varied forms in different parts of Europe (p.235). The PBF studies in Europe often focus only on a few systems. For instance, Frølich *et al.* (2010) have compared Denmark, Norway, and Portugal for the impact of PBF on academics and institutions. In another study, Jongbloed and Vossensteyn (2001) compared eleven OECD countries, of which seven were European. They identified that some countries were more oriented towards PBF than the other. However, they concluded with a surprise that despite the focus on accountability and quality issues in public debates, most of the countries in their sample were not mainly geared towards PBF both for teaching as well as research (p.135). Frølich (2008), in his study, compared five European systems that adopted PBF. However, neither Jongbloed and Vossensteyn (2001) nor Frølich (2008) identified the various

macro and micro determinants of new accountability policies and how these factors could hinder the impact of PBF. A broad study, covering all European systems, on determinants of adoption and diffusion of PBF, has not been conducted before. So, the proposed research on the determinants will contribute to policymaking by helping decisionmakers better understand the conditions that are fertile for broader acceptance, effectiveness, and endurance of these systems.

To investigate the contextual factors, we intend to conduct a quantitative study of all European systems, including early adopters, late adopters, and nonadopters of the PBF model. However, we first need a conceptual framework that fully encompasses the contextual factors of European higher education. Thus, this paper aims to develop a conceptual framework that can explain the adoption and diffusion of PBF models in various European systems over the past 30 years, taking into account the peculiarities of European higher education systems. Specifically, we will address this research question: what are the characteristics of European countries/provinces/states that have adopted performance funding over the past 30 years?

Investigating the contextual factors for the spread of the PBF model is essential because, without this understanding, it will be difficult to identify the real challenges higher education systems are facing worldwide.

This paper is organized into four sections. In the first section, we have discussed existing conceptual frameworks for studying the adoption and diffusion of higher education policies and have proposed an alternative conceptual framework to understand the adoption and diffusion of higher education policies in European countries. At the end of this section, eight research hypotheses for the initial assessment of the proposed conceptual framework are also given. The second section explains the research design, including data collection and analysis methods. In the third section, the results of our descriptive study are given. In the fourth section, we have discussed our findings. In the final section, the conceptual implications of the results are discussed.

Conceptual Framework for Understanding Adoption and Diffusion of PBF Model

Many scholars argue that state higher education policy adoption should be studied in the broader contexts in which higher education systems operate. These contexts include the political, ideological, and economic context of a country, historical and institutional context of higher education, and the globalized international context (James C Hearn *et al.*, 2017; Johnstone & Marcucci, 2010). James C. Hearn *et al.* (2017) have conceptualized these contexts into a theoretical framework for understanding policy adoption and diffusion at the state level in the US higher education. This framework highlights the importance of four different contextual factors for the adoption and diffusion of the PBF model.

First is a state's *socioeconomic context*, which can be comprised of its demographic, educational, and economic factors. Demographic factors may include 'population size,' 'age-group distribution,' 'population growth rate,' 'population density,' and so on. Among the educational factors, important variables are 'educational attainment levels' and 'postsecondary enrollment rate,' and so forth. Finally, economic indicators may comprise of 'gross state product (GSP),' 'GSP per capita,' 'GSP per-capita growth,' 'median per-capita income,' and 'unemployment rate,' and so on.

Second, a state's *organizational and policy context* that is dependent upon two broad factors: organizational ecology and policy. Organizational ecology describes the 'number and

the proportional distribution of institutions by control level,' 'the number and proportional distribution of students by institutional sector,' 'student migration pattern,' 'number and strength of research institutions in the state,' and 'agency research capacity,' and so on. The policy describes the 'postsecondary funding,' 'tuition,' and 'enrollment patterns.'

Third, a state's *politico-institutional context*, which includes political ideology, legislative professionalism, partisanship, electoral conditions, gubernatorial strength and tenure, and interest group climate. Political ideology and legislative professionalism can be measured by 'state ideology indicators' and 'Squire Index' respectively. Partisanship is dependent upon 'legislative/gubernatorial party affiliations and strengths', and so forth. Electoral conditions are determined by the 'degree of parties' electoral competitiveness' and 'election timing,' and so forth. Gubernatorial strength and tenure depend upon 'constitutional authority' and 'time in office' or the length of the governor's tenure, and so on. Finally, interest-group climate depends upon 'interest-group characteristics (density, strengths, concentration)' and 'governance arrangements (consolidated governing board across institutional sectors, strong coordinating board, weak coordinating board, planning agency).'

Fourth is a state's *policy diffusion context*, which may include decision efficiency, competitive advantage, normative pressures, and coercive pressures. Decision efficiency indicates a state's capability to learn from other states' actual experiences with policy choices, thus, informing and ideally improving its policy choices. Competitive advantage represents a state's desire to adopt policies for positioning itself to better compete with other states. Normative pressures involve adopting policies favored by regional or national-level peers, intermediary organizations, and policy entrepreneurs. Finally, coercive pressures involve adopting policies imposed by critical outside resource providers.

However, James C Hearn et al. (2017) have developed their framework in the US higher education context where despite political interference on various occasions, higher education has been mainly coordinated by the market mechanism (Hearn & Ness, 2017, p.20). Therefore, the application of this conceptual model to the world's other region demands a fundamental investigation of how higher education systems are coordinated in those parts of the world.

Clark (1983) conceptualized the authority relationship between universities and other societal actors as a three-dimensional space illustrated by a triangle. The three ends of the triangle represent the three different forms of coordination in a higher education system, i.e., *the nation state's authority, market, and the academic oligarchy*. The state authority is comprised of political actors and the state bureaucracy, whereas academic oligarchy represents the faculty members, their collegial bodies, and interest groups. In his cross-national study of eight systems, USSR and Sweden, though different from each other, were examples of systems where state authority had a crucial role in coordinating higher education. Italy represented a system where academic oligarchy had a stronger role, whereas the market was the dominant player in the coordination of US higher education. Although academics in the US play a role in accreditation and quality (Hearn & Ness, 2017), Clark's argued that the role of academic oligarchy was almost absent in the US at the state or national levels. Other countries, namely France, Britain, Canada, and Japan, had mixed forms of coordination with varying degrees of influence from the three sources of authority.

Brennan (2010) noted that despite many changes in higher education, some of Clark's concepts are still very relevant today. In the next few paragraphs, we have discussed some of the changing trends which have emerged in European higher education during the last three decades.

Trends and Peculiarities in European Higher Education:

Since Clark's (1983) seminal work, it is easy to see numerous trends of consistency and change in European systems at the institutional, national, and supranational levels. On the one hand, some changes at the institutional level are coming through the voluntary actions of academic oligarchy in their efforts to forge networks with businesses for the sustenance of academic enterprise. In these divergent changes, academics were "not just as players being 'corporatized'" but acted as institutional entrepreneurs (Slaughter & Rhoades, 2004, p.12). Consequently, many European universities have been adopting entrepreneurial style (Clark, 1998). On the other hand, isomorphic pressures—coercive, normative, or mimetic —(DiMaggio & Powell, 1983) also driving the change. The most important isomorphic pressures in Europe are coming from national and supranational actors, namely the nation-states, the European Union (EU), the Organization of Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD), and intergovernmental initiatives, such as Bologna Process.

At the national level, Capano (2011) has captured contextual changes in his governance typology. Contrary to many scholars, he contended that governments, though have changed their role, are still significant actors in the governance of society and higher education. He further assumed that due to changes in the environment, a government chooses a level of its involvement in specifying systemic *goals* and also chooses a level of its involvement in specifying the *means* to pursue those goals. Based on the government's two levels of involvement in setting goals and identifying means, Capano (2011) identified four modes of governance in European higher education, namely 'hierarchical mode,' 'procedural mode,' 'steering at the distance mode,' and 'self-governance mode.'

For capturing supranational drivers of change, Riyad A. Shahjahan and Kezar (2013) have warned higher education scholars about "methodological nationalism," the assumption that the national boundaries define the unit of analysis for a society. Riyad A Shahjahan (2012) has identified the EU and OECD as two significant supranational actors, which without having competence in European higher education, play their role as a discursive force, networker, and coordinator, and due to their multiple muscles.

Moreover, an open method of coordination (OMC) is an important mode of governance which EU has adopted during the last two decades for different policy areas, including education (Gornitzka, 2006; Radaelli, 2003; Veiga & Amaral, 2006). OMC can be comprised of various components, including 'guidelines,' 'benchmarking and sharing of best practices,' and 'indicators' (Radaelli, 2003, p.15).

Nevertheless, the role of IOs, or their saliency, is contingent upon "material, cultural, and intellectual resources" of a nation-state. These IOs converge and diverge on various policy-related issues; therefore, it not easy to generalize on their practices (Riyad A Shahjahan, 2012). Despite global isomorphism, there are differences in various systems and institutions across the globe (Brennan, 2010) because globalization sometimes creates a convergence of policies, but other times it may lead to heterogeneous outcomes when local actors exercise their agency (Vaira, 2004, p.484). Therefore, we have identified here the various initiatives at all three levels, which can have implications for PBF adoption in the European higher education space.

A Framework for Studying Adoption and Diffusion of PBF in Europe:

Funding, quality, changing demographics, the role of academics in institutional governance, institutional autonomy, the third mission, university-business relationship, and the

emergence of the European higher education market are some of the factors which have implications for universities and higher education policies. We have briefly described some of these factors here.

Many countries in Europe have introduced tuition and fees, but with many variations in the tuition level and accompanied grants. As most of the systems in Europe are comparatively more dependent upon state funding, the tuition level can be an essential factor in the adoption of the new funding model (European Commission, 2018b).

Amongst the most important demographic factor in Europe is the aging population. Although the trend is not consistent across all European countries, the working-age population is shrinking in Europe (European Commission, 2018a). These demographic changes have severe implications for higher education (Orr, 2010). Consequently, lifelong learning has become an essential agenda item on the European level. So, universities will have to develop more academic programs for the non-traditional population (Brine, 2006).

The role of academic oligarchy is also very different across European states. It is diminishing in some countries, but in some countries, it is mostly unchanged in institutional governance (Arimoto *et al.*, 2013; De Boer *et al.*, 2008). These trends can have profound implications for the adoption of new policies.

Among the most important initiatives of the EU are the European Higher Education Modernization Agenda which aims to promote quality, accountability, institutional autonomy, the PBF, competition, alternative funding sources for higher education including private funding, and modernizing university human resource systems for supporting researchers mobility (European Commission, 2011b). Many actions have already been taken to realize the modernization agenda. For instance, the European University Association (EUA), through various European Commission funded projects, has already developed an autonomy scorecard¹ for comparing the institutional autonomy in all European higher education systems, University Efficiency Hub² for helping universities to learn the best practices from their European peers to promote efficiency in their operations, and Public Funding Observatory³ for comparing state-level support for higher education. The effects of these reforms are now visible in many countries, for instance, De Boer *et al.* (2008) reported in a comparative study that competition for money, personnel, and prestige has increased within and between universities in Austria, England, Germany, and the Netherland. Many other proposals of the European Commission, such as the "Single Market Act" (European Commission, 2011a) and "A Reinforced European Research Area Partnership for Excellence and Growth (European Commission, 2012)", are complementing the higher education modernization agenda. European Research Area (ERA) is another initiative of the EU which is aimed to create an open labor market for researchers by ensuring researchers' mobility within European states (European Commission, 2012, p.3). So, ERA is strengthening the form of market coordination in European higher education systems. Moreover, the EU has been investing in research and innovation since the beginning. In 2015, one year after the Horizon 2020 was launched, European universities were the biggest beneficiaries of this program (European Commission, 2015, p.16). In fluctuating funding at the state level, European universities have been dependent upon the EU money and therefore seem willing to adopt many top-down reforms.

¹ <https://www.university-autonomy.eu/>

² <http://efficiency.eua.eu/>

³ <http://efficiency.eua.eu/public-funding-observatory>

Bologna Process (BP), a significant intergovernmental initiative, is aimed to create a common European Higher Education Area (EHEA) by promoting students' and staff mobility and enhancing graduate employability through harmonizing the degree structures across Europe (BFUG Secretariat, 2019).

Figure 1 shows how these institutional, state, and supranational actors form a higher education coordination pentagon. Coordination among these actors takes place in various contexts, which are depicted in the figure. These contextual factors provide enablements and constraints to all the actors that can ultimately affect the adoption and diffusion of PBF in European higher education.

Figure 1: A Conceptual Framework for Understanding PBF Adoption and Diffusion in European Higher Education Systems

As a next step, we needed to identify the most current and relevant indicators for all the actors and contexts we have identified here and then need their operationalization. So far, we could identify only a few variables of supranational influence, which can be substantial antecedents of higher education policies at the state level in Europe. For example, European Innovation Index, Net Contribution by a state to European Budget. In Europe, some countries are a net contributor to European exchequers, such as Germany, France, Italy, Austria, and others are net recipients, such as Latvia, Hungary, Estonia, Romania, and Greece. Countries that are net recipients may face more coercive pressures from the European Commission to adopt policies that European Commission favor. The following are eight hypotheses to collect preliminary evidence for the validity of the conceptual framework discussed above.

Study Hypotheses:

Through the above conceptual framework, this study will focus only on eight possible predictors of adopting the performance-based funding model.

Johnstone and Marcucci (2010) have suggested that as a country's capacity to tax its citizen reduces, higher education funding move towards cost-sharing and more accountability. The tax revenue of a state is also linked with its economic condition. Thus, we hypothesize that a state with higher tax revenue as a percentage of its GDP and poor economic condition will have more incentive to ensure that the public higher education institutions are making wise decisions is utilizing scarce public resources and will more likely to adopt accountability policies for higher education.

Hypothesis 1: A country with a higher level of tax revenue as a percentage of GDP will be more likely to adopt a performance-based funding model.

Hypothesis 2: A country with a poor economic climate (or lower GDP growth rate) will be more likely to adopt a performance-based funding model.

McLendon et al. (2006) have indicated that higher education provides economic opportunities. The countries with poor economic conditions feel more pressure to promote efficiency and accountability in their higher education systems. Johnstone and Marcucci (2010) have suggested that as a country's growing young population, expanding tertiary level enrollment and increasing tertiary education expenditure put pressure on the higher education system. These factors, in turn, raise capacity and accountability challenges. Thus, we hypothesize the following:

Hypothesis 3: A country with a larger population will be more likely to adopt a performance-based funding model.

Hypothesis 4: A country with a higher population growth rate will be more likely to adopt a performance-based funding model.

Hypothesis 5: A country with a larger youth population (of aged between 20 to 24 years) will be more likely to adopt a performance-based funding model.

Hypothesis 6: A country with a greater total numeric tertiary level enrollment will be more likely to adopt a performance-based funding model.

Hypothesis 7: A country with a higher level of gross tertiary enrollment rate will be more likely to adopt a performance-based funding model.

Hypothesis 8: A country with a higher level of tertiary education expenditure (as a percentage of total educational expenditure) will be more likely to adopt a performance-based funding model.

In the conceptual framework above, the role of the EU in promoting accountability policies in higher education could be investigated by hypothesizing a country's financial dependence on the EU, which can, in turn, be operationalized as a country's net contribution towards European exchequer. If a country has a negative net contribution, the country will be more dependent upon the EU. To this end, data for net contribution to the EU were collected directly from the EU Budget Office's website. However, the data were available only from 2000 and onwards. Therefore, no hypothesis is included in this study about the role of the EU in determining higher education policies at the state level in Europe.

Research Design

Study Data:

As we are interested in investigating governmental behavior and characteristics across the various European states and over time, our dataset will incorporate both temporal and spatial dimensions. In the spatial dimension, this study includes 21 European countries, namely Austria(AUT), Bulgaria(BGR), Croatia(HRV), Cyprus(CYP), Denmark(DNK), Estonia(EST), Finland(FIN), France(FRA), Greece(GRC), Iceland(ISL), Ireland(IRE), Italy(ITA), Latvia(LVA), Lithuania(LTU), Malta(MLT), Norway(NOR), Portugal(PRT), Romania(ROU), Sweden(SWE), Switzerland(CHE), and Netherland(NLD). Although the United Kingdom was the first European country that adopted performance-based funding in 1985, it is not included in this study because it has a different government structure than the other European countries. France was the next country that adopted a PBF model in 1988 and is included in this study. Malta, Cyprus, Iceland, and Lithuania have so far not adopted the new funding model. Greece has just adopted the new funding model in January 2020. The year of adoption of PBF is critical in this study. We collected the adoption year data mostly directly from the Education Ministries or other regulatory organizations in each European country. However, in a few cases, we collected this information from a European University Association(EUA) report (Claeys-Kulik & Eastermann, 2015).

Broadly, there are two types of countries: countries that have adopted the PBF model and the others that did not. Following the leader-laggard model of policy diffusion (Weible & Sabatier, 2018, p. 264), we divided the adopter countries into "leaders" and "laggards." Leaders are those countries that were the earliest adopters of the PBF model between 1988 and 2002. However, within the leaders, we have further made two groups. Five countries adopted the PBF model between 1988 and 1994 are included in the Leader-group-A. Four countries adopted the PBF model between 1998 and 2002 are included in the Leader-group-B. The list of all the countries, the year of their adoption of the PBF model, and their group are given in Table 1.

Table 1: List of countries included in this study, the year they adopted the PBF model for teaching-related funding, and their group in terms of the 'leader,' the 'laggard,' or the nonadopters

Country	Year PBF Adopted	Group
France	1988	Leader-Group A
Denmark	1994	Leader-Group A
Italy	1994	Leader-Group A
Portugal	1994	Leader-Group A
Sweden	1994	Leader-Group A
Finland	1998	Leader-Group B
Switzerland	1999	Leader-Group B
Austria	2002	Leader-Group B
Norway	2002	Leader-Group B
Netherland	2012	Laggards
Croatia	2012	Laggards
Romania	2012	Laggards
Ireland	2013	Laggards
Bulgaria	2015	Laggards
Latvia	2015	Laggards
Estonia	2017	Laggards
Greece	2020	Laggards

Iceland	-	Nonadopter
Cyprus	-	Nonadopter
Lithuania **	-	Nonadopter
Malta	-	Nonadopter

** Lithuania has already adopted the PBF model for research funding in 2001.

Based on the previous studies conducted in the US on adoption and diffusion of PBF policies, 48 contextual variables were identified, and the data were downloaded from two databases: OECD⁴ and World Bank⁵. However, only eight variables are chosen for this study.

In the temporal dimension, this study will use the data for eight independent variables for a period from 1983 to 2018. However, for the analysis, we used six years of data of each country, including the year it adopted the PBF model (if it was an adopter) and five years preceding the adoption.

The list of all the variables is given in Table 2.

Table 2: List of variables used in this study

Variable #	Variable Title	Variable Description	Source
Variable 1	tax_to_gdp_1	Tax revenue (% of GDP)	World Bank
Variable 2	gdp_ga%_2	GDP growth (% annual)	World Bank
Variable 3	tot_pop_3	The total numeric population of a country	World Bank
Variable 4	pop_grwth_4	Population growth rate (%)	World Bank
Variable 5	pop_20to24_5	Youth (20 to 24 years of age) per 100K of the total population of a country	OECD (data were converted to per 100k population ourselves)
Variable 6	tert_enrol_tot_6	Gross tertiary level enrollment (ISCED2011, Levels 5 to 8)	OECD and our own calculation
Variable 7	tert_enr_rate_7	Tertiary education enrolment gross (% of total) ⁶	World Bank
Variable 8	tert_exp_pgexpe_8	Expenditure on tertiary education (% of government expenditure on education)	World Bank

As the data for variable 6, 'gross tertiary level enrollment (ISCED2011, Levels 5 to 8)', were not available for all the countries, and for all the years, we calculated these data ourselves. To do this, we multiplied the number of 20 to 24 years youth (these data were collected from the OECD) with the 'tertiary education enrolment gross(% of total)' (variable 7). The calculated values were compared with the OECD data for the instances where data were available in the OECD database. In most cases, there was little discrepancy.

⁴ <https://stats.oecd.org/>

⁵ <https://databank.worldbank.org/reports.aspx?source=world-development-indicators#>

⁶ Gross enrollment ratio is the ratio of total enrollment, regardless of age, to the population of the age group that officially corresponds to that level of education.

Analytical Methods:

The aim of this study is not to draw any causal inference about the adoption of the PBF model in any European country. Instead, our aim is to see the similarities and differences across the countries and over time in terms of the adoption of the PBF model for higher education. To this end, we performed some descriptive analyses to find preliminary evidence for our proposed conceptual framework. So, we looked either at the trend of a variable, for instance, GDP Growth (variable 2 of this study), or calculated the percentage change in a variable for six years, i.e., the five years before a country adopted the PBF model and the year in which it adopted the PBF model. For instance, we calculated the percentage growth in Tax Revenue as % of GDP (i.e., variable 1 of this study) of France as follows:

$$\% \text{ Growth} = \% \Delta_{t-5 \text{ to } t} = ((Var_1 \text{ at } t-5 - Var_1 \text{ at } t) / Var_1 \text{ at } t-5) * 100$$

Since France adopted the PBF model in 1988, t-5 was 1983, and t (the year it adopted the PBF model) was 1988.

However, for nonadopter countries, we calculated the percentage growth of various variables between 2013 and 2018, the latest years for which data were available. For comparing the different groups, which are identified in Table 1, we also calculated the mean change(μ) in each group.

Empirical Findings

Figure 2 to Figure 5 shows the GDP growth trend in all the countries. Table 3 to Table 6 show the percentage of growth in variables 1, 5,6,7,8 of this study. Data in Table 3 to Table 6 are also displayed graphically in Figure 6 to Figure 8. Our analysis indicated that in most of these countries, the total population (variable 3) was either shrinking or was almost stagnant, i.e., the population growth rate (variable 4) was minimal for the time period we calculated their percentage growth. Similarly, youth population of aged 20 to 24 years (variable 5) was also shrinking during the same period in almost all countries, except in Portugal(1989-1994), Finland(1993-1998), and Netherland(2007-2012) with a total growth of 2.18%, 1.15%, 5.94% respectively. The growth rate of the youth population aged 20 to 24 years can be seen in Table 3, Table 4, Table 5, and Table 6 for the leaders-group-A, leaders-group-B, laggards, and nonadopters respectively. Therefore, we can eliminate the variables 3 and 4 as possible predictors of the adoption of the PBF model in most of the countries.

Next, we looked at the trend of variable-2 and the percentage growth in variable 1, 5, 6, 7, and 8. If the trend or the percentage growth in a variable and the behavior of the country in terms of adoption of the PBF model were in the direction we hypothesized in the beginning, we say that the data support our hypothesis. So, we put a 'Yes' in the relevant cell in Table 7; otherwise, we put 'No' in the relevant cell. However, in some cases, the trend or the percentage growth in the variable was not very significant; therefore, it was hard to say that the data support our hypotheses. Thus, we put 'May Be (MB)' in the relevant cell. Finally, in some cases, data were not available; therefore, we put DNA, i.e., Data Not Available, in those cells.

Discussion

We have first interpreted the results given in Table 7 for the individual countries within each group, and then we analyzed how different groups of countries differ across the variables of our study. Finally, we analyzed what the laggards were like in terms of the variables of our

study in the year 2000. In other words, were there more or fewer chances of their adoption of the PBF model in 2000.

Intra group-level analysis:

Leaders-Group-A: Figure 2 shows that the 'GDP growth rate (annual %)' in France was increasing between 1983 and 1988. Data in Table 3 and Figure 6 to Figure 8 indicate that while 'Tax revenue (as % of GDP)' in France decreased (-1.19%), gross tertiary enrolment (var 6) increased by 14.28%, tertiary enrolment rate (var 7) increased by 12.98%, and the tertiary expenditure (var 8) increased by 7.67% during the same time period. So, the increase in the numeric tertiary level enrolment, tertiary enrolment rate, and tertiary education expenditure (as a percentage of total educational expenditure) seem related to the adoption of the PBF model in 1988.

Similarly, in Denmark and Sweden, gross tertiary enrolment (var 6), tertiary enrolment rate (var 7), and the tertiary expenditure (var 8) increased from 1989 to 1994. In both countries, the GDP growth rate was declining during the said period. Also, the tax revenue (as % of GDP)(var 1) also increased slightly (0.52 %) in Denmark. Nevertheless, tax revenue (as % of GDP)(var 1) declined significantly (30.41%) in Sweden. So, Sweden is a compelling case where the PBF model was adopted in the rapidly declining Tax rate.

In Italy, GDP growth rate (var 2) was declining, tax revenue as % of GDP (var 1) increased by 4.79 %, gross tertiary enrolment (var 6) increased by 36.2%, tertiary enrolment rate (var 7) increased by 42.75%, and the tertiary expenditure (var 8) increased slightly by 0.20 % from 1989 to 1994. Finally, in Portugal also, while GDP growth rate was declining, tax revenue as % of GDP (var 1) increased slightly by 9.10 %, youth population of 20 to 24 years of age (var 5) increased by 2.18 %, gross tertiary enrolment (var 6) increased by 72.98 %, and tertiary enrolment rate (var 7) increased by 67.46 %. However, the tertiary expenditure (var 8) decreased significantly by 9.25 % from 1989 to 1994. Table 7 shows that the data support three, four, four, five, and four hypotheses of this study for France, Denmark, Italy, Portugal, and Sweden respectively.

Leaders-Group-B: Table 4 and Figure 6 to Figure 8 shows that in all of these countries, gross tertiary enrolment (var 6) and tertiary enrolment rate (var 7) increased significantly in the years preceding the adoption of the PBF model. Similarly, in all of the four countries, Tax revenue as % of GDP (var 1) and the tertiary expenditure (var 8) increased to a varying degree, except in Austria, where despite an increase in tertiary enrolment rate by 16.45%, tertiary expenditure declined significantly by 13.96%. Figure 3 shows that in this group, while Austria and Norway had a declining GDP growth rate (var 2), Finland had a very high rate, except in the year the PBF model was adopted. Table 7 shows that the data support three, four, three, and five hypotheses of this study for Finland, Switzerland, Austria, and Norway respectively.

Figure 2: GDP Growth Rate (annual %) in the "leaders" (group-A) for the year PBF model was adopted (year 6) and five years preceding it (Year 1 to 5)

Figure 3: GDP Growth Rate (annual %) in the "leaders" (group-B) for the year PBF model was adopted (year 6) and five years preceding it (Year 1 to 5)

Figure 4: GDP Growth Rate (annual %) in the "laggards" for the year PBF model was adopted (year 6) and five years preceding it (Year 1 to 5)

Figure 5: GDP Growth Rate (annual %) in the nonadopter countries for the last six years (2013-2018) for which data were available

Table 3: Percentage growth in five variables ('tax revenue (% of GDP)', '20-to-24 years population/100K total population', 'gross tertiary level enrollment', 'tertiary education participation rate(% of relevant age group)', and 'percentage of tertiary education expenditure (as % of total educational expenditure)' in the "leaders" (group A) during the last six years which include the year PBF model was adopted (t) and five years preceding it (t-5).

Leaders(A)	tax_to_gdp_1 @ t-5	tax_to_gdp_1 @ t	% Δ t-5 to t	pop_20to24_5 @ t-5	pop_20to24_5 @ t	% Δ t-5 to t	tert_enrol _tot_6 @ t-5	tert_enrol _tot_6 @ t	% Δ t-5 to t	tert_enr _rate_7 @ t-5	tert_enr _rate_7 @ t	% Δ t-5 to t	tert_exp_ pgexpe_8 @ t-5	tert_exp_ pgexpe_8 @ t	% Δ t-5 to t
	Variable 1			Variable 5			Variable 6			Variable 7			Variable 8		
Denmark	31.40	31.56	0.52	7945	7155	-9.95	129,901	166,334	28.05	31.85	44.66	40.18	17.88	25.91	44.93
France	19.44	19.21	-1.19	7597	7471	-1.67	1,159,496	1,325,077	14.28	27.24	30.78	12.98	13.35	14.38	7.67
Italy	23.95	25.09	4.79	8198	7798	-4.87	1,303,839	1,775,860	36.20	28.07	40.06	42.75	16.03	16.06	0.20
Portugal	17.74	19.35	9.10	7843	8014	2.18	154,757	267,692	72.98	19.97	33.43	67.46	18.36	16.66	-9.25
Sweden	21.46	14.94	-30.41	7271	6631	-8.80	186,433	231,680	24.27	30.19	39.79	31.80	21.68	25.32	16.79
Mean			-3.44			-4.62			35.16			39.03			12.07

Table 4: Percentage growth in five variables ('tax revenue (% of GDP)', '20-to-24 years population/100K total population', 'gross tertiary level enrollment', 'tertiary education participation rate(% of relevant age group)', and 'percentage of tertiary education expenditure (as % of total educational expenditure)' in the "leaders" (group B) during the last six years which include the year PBF model was adopted (t) and five years preceding it (t-5).

Leaders(B)	tax_to_gdp_1 @ t-5	tax_to_gdp_1 @ t	% Δ t-5 to t	pop_20to24_5 @ t-5	pop_20to24_5 @ t	% Δ t-5 to t	tert_enrol _tot_6 @ t-5	tert_enrol _tot_6 @ t	% Δ t-5 to t	tert_enr _rate_7 @ t-5	tert_enr _rate_7 @ t	% Δ t-5 to t	tert_exp_ pgexpe_8 @ t-5	tert_exp_ pgexpe_8 @ t	% Δ t-5 to t
	Variable 1			Variable 5			Variable 6			Variable 7			Variable 8		
Finland	22.42	22.71	1.29	6177	6247	1.15	185,764	254,903	37.22	59.36	79.17	33.37	28.23	28.33	0.35
Switzerland	7.92	9.04	14.07	6645	5769	-13.19	141,589	152,468	7.68	30.46	36.99	21.43	20.51	22.31	8.80
Austria	26.80	26.98	0.66	6269	6046	-3.57	247,613	282,036	13.90	49.57	57.72	16.45	26.23	22.57	-13.96
Norway	23.89	27.19	13.80	6780	6037	-10.96	183,683	200,885	9.36	61.50	73.33	19.23	26.50	27.50	3.77
Mean			7.46			-6.64			17.04			22.62			-0.26

Table 5: Percentage growth in five variables ('tax revenue (% of GDP)', '20-to-24 years population/100K total population', 'gross tertiary level enrollment', 'tertiary education participation rate(% of relevant age group)', and 'percentage of tertiary education expenditure (as % of total educational expenditure)' in the "laggards" during the last six years which include the year PBF model was adopted (t) and five years preceding it (t-5).

Laggards	tax_to_gdp_1 @ t-5	tax_to_gdp_1 @ t	% Δ t-5 to t	pop_20to24_5 @ t-5	pop_20to24_5 @ t	% Δ t-5 to t	tert_enrol _tot_6 @ t-5	tert_enrol _tot_6 @ t	% Δ t-5 to t	tert_enr _rate_7 @ t-5	tert_enr _rate_7 @ t	% Δ t-5 to t	tert_exp_ pgexpe_8 @ t-5	tert_exp_ pgexpe_8 @ t	% Δ t-5 to t
	Variable 1			Variable 5			Variable 6			Variable 7			Variable 8		
Netherland	21.60	19.41	-10.13	5933	6285	5.94	582,574	806,754	38.48	59.94	76.61	27.80			
Croatia	21.21	19.75	-6.91	8322	6032	-27.52	132,475	155,582	17.44	47.19	60.65	28.52	19.80	22.16	11.89
Romania	17.54	17.93	2.23	6665	5433	-18.49	891,516	652,317	-26.83	58.28	49.71	-14.70	26.33	26.16	-0.65
Ireland	23.75	22.88	-3.65	6513	6011	-7.71	201,827	199,965	-0.92	54.02	71.70	32.73	23.26	21.51	-7.51
Bulgaria	18.45	20.20	9.49	7140	5199	-27.18	284,864	274,141	-3.76	57.80	70.30	21.64	14.81	15.92	7.49
Latvia	19.79	22.50	13.71	7609	6014	-20.97	110,206	88,357	-19.83	69.05	74.30	7.60	15.88	22.09	39.09
Estonia	19.80	20.98	5.95	7325	6542	-10.70	68,349	47,694	-30.22	72.38	69.64	-3.79	21.82	27.12	24.27
Greece	24.02	26.19	9.05	5518	5117	-7.28	704,205	750,586	6.59	116.38	136.60	17.38			
Mean			2.47			-14.24			-2.38			14.65			9.32

Table 6: Percentage growth in five variables ('tax revenue (% of GDP)', '20-to-24 years population/100K total population', 'gross tertiary level enrollment', 'tertiary education participation rate(% of relevant age group)', and 'percentage of tertiary education expenditure (as % of total educational expenditure)' in the nonadopters during the last six years (2013-2018) for which data were available (t-5 = 2013, t = 2018)

Non Adopters	tax_to_gdp_1 @ t-5	tax_to_gdp_1 @ t	% Δ t-5 to t	pop_20to24_5 @ t-5	pop_20to24_5 @ t	% Δ t-5 to t	tert_enrol _tot_6 @ t-5	tert_enrol _tot_6 @ t	% Δ t-5 to t	tert_enr _rate_7 @ t-5	tert_enr _rate_7 @ t	% Δ t-5 to t	tert_exp_ pgexpe_8 @ t-5	tert_exp_ pgexpe_8 @ t	% Δ t-5 to t
	Variable 1			Variable 5			Variable 6			Variable 7			Variable 8		
Iceland	21.97	23.32	6.13	7586	7302	-3.74	19,722	18,287	-7.28	80.30	71.85	-10.53	19.36	19.91	2.85
Cyprus	23.60	24.05	1.89	6056	5425	-10.42	32,921	49,930	51.67	47.53	75.94	59.79	22.40	20.78	-7.23
Lithuania	15.63	16.63	6.46	7234	5797	-19.87	157,338	126,135	-19.83	73.53	72.42	-1.52	28.76	20.52	-28.65
Malta	26.74	26.46	-1.07	7141	6462	-9.51	13,351	16,740	25.38	43.89	54.26	23.62	19.25	25.33	31.59
Mean			3.35			-10.89			12.49			17.84			-0.36

Figure 6: Percentage growth in the "Tax revenue (% of GDP)" in all the countries (adopters and nonadopters) for six years. For adopters, these years include the year PBF model was adopted and five years preceding it, and for nonadopters, these years are 2013-2018 (the years for which data were available).

Figure 7: Percentage growth of "tertiary enrollment rate (%)" in all the countries (adopters and nonadopters) for six years. For adopters, these years include the year PBF model was adopted and five years preceding it and for nonadopters, these years are 2013-2018 (the years for which data were available).

Figure 8: Percentage growth in "tertiary education expenditure (as % of governmental educational expenditure)" in all the countries (adopters and nonadopters) for six years. For adopters, these years include the year PBF model was adopted and five years preceding it and for nonadopters, these years are 2013-2018 (the years for which data were available)

Laggards: Table 6 and Figure 6 to Figure 8 show that in five out of eight countries in this group, tax revenue as % of GDP (var 1) increased during six years. However, in the three countries (Netherlands, Ireland, and Croatia), tax revenue as % of GDP decreased during this time. In six out of eight of these countries, the tertiary enrolment rate (var 7) increased, except in Romania and Estonia. Ironically, the tertiary expenditure (var 8) decreased significantly by 7.51% in Ireland. However, in four other countries, it increased. Data for Greece and Netherlands were not available for variable 8. Also, Figure 4 shows that in five out of the eight countries, the GDP growth rate was declining when PBF was adopted. Finally, Table 7 shows that the data support four, four, one, two, three, four, two, and four hypotheses of this study for Netherlands, Croatia, Romania, Ireland, Bulgaria, Latvia, Estonia, and Greece respectively.

Nonadopters: Figure 5 shows that in all of the four nonadopter islands countries, GDP growth rate (var 2) was either increasing or had a better value. Table 6 and Figure 6 to Figure 8 show that while the tertiary enrolment rate (var 7) increased substantially in Cyprus by 59.79% and Malta by 23.62%, both the countries did not adopt the PBF model. In Cyprus, this increase was

combined with a significant decrease (7.23%) in the tertiary expenditure (var 8) at the time when the economy was doing well. Malta is a compelling case in this group where increased gross tertiary enrolment, enrolment rate, tertiary expenditure, and tax to GDP rate did not result in the adoption of the PBF model. Finally, Table 7 shows that the data support four, three, five, and three hypotheses of this study for Cyprus, Iceland, Lithuania, and Malta respectively.

Table 7: Results of the study hypotheses (A 'Yes' means that the data suggest support for our hypothesis, and a 'No' means otherwise. 'MB' means that the data did not suggest anything.

	Country	Var 1	Var 2	Var 5	Var 6	Var 7	Var 8
Leaders-A	France	No	No	No	Yes	Yes	Yes
	Denmark	No	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	Yes
	Italy	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	No
	Portugal	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	No
	Sweden	No	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	Yes
Leaders-B	Finland	MB	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	No
	Switzerland	Yes	MB	No	Yes	Yes	Yes
	Austria	MB	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	No
	Norway	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	Yes
Laggards	Netherland	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	DNA
	Croatia	No	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	Yes
	Romania	Yes	MB	No	No	No	No
	Ireland	No	Yes	No	No	Yes	No
	Bulgaria	Yes	MB	No	No	Yes	Yes
	Latvia	Yes	Yes	No	No	Yes	Yes
	Estonia	Yes	MB	No	No	No	Yes
	Greece	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	DNA
Nonadopters	Cyprus	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	Yes
	Iceland	No	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	No
	Lithuania	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
	Malta	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	No	No

Group Comparison:

In this section, we have analyzed how various groups (Leader-A, Leader-B, Laggards, and Nonadopters) differ from each other in terms of the adoption of the PBF model. For this analysis, we look at the mean values of the percentage growth in Tax revenue as % of GDP (var 1), youth population of 20 to 24 years of age (var 5), gross tertiary enrolment (var 6), tertiary enrolment rate (var 7), and the tertiary expenditure as a percentage of governmental expenditure on education (var 8), which are given in Table 3 to Table 6 and are also illustrated in Figure 6 to Figure 8. During the six years' time slot of our analysis, the mean values of the percentage growth in 'Tax revenue as % of GDP' (var 1) for leaders-group-A, leaders-group-B, laggards, and nonadopters were -3.44, 7.46, 2.47, and 3.35 respectively. The mean of the leaders-group-A was significantly affected by Sweden, where Tax revenue as % of GDP' (var 1) was substantially decreased by 30.41% during the six years. Nevertheless, this mean value was higher for leaders-group-B ($\mu = 7.46\%$) than the mean value of the laggards ($\mu = 2.47\%$). On the other hand, the laggards had a lower mean value ($\mu = 2.47\%$) than the nonadopters ($\mu = 3.35\%$). While the higher mean value of the leaders-group-B suggests the possibility of early

adoption of the PBF model in this group, a lower mean value of the laggards than nonadopters contradicts this possibility.

Nevertheless, Leaders-group-A, had the lowest percentage decrease in 'youth population of 20 to 24 years of age (var 5)' ($\mu = -4.62\%$), highest increase in 'gross tertiary enrolment (var 6)' ($\mu = 35.16\%$), 'tertiary enrolment rate (var 7)' ($\mu = 39.03\%$), and 'tertiary expenditure (var 8)' ($\mu = 12.07\%$) than all the other groups. Similarly, Leaders-group-B had the lesser decrease in 'youth population of 20 to 24 years of age (var 5)' ($\mu = -6.64\%$), more increase in the 'gross tertiary enrolment (var 6)' ($\mu = 17.04\%$) and the 'tertiary enrolment rate (var 7)' ($\mu = 22.62\%$) than the 'laggards'. However, there was decrease ($\mu = -0.26\%$) in the 'tertiary expenditure (var 8)' in Leaders-group-B, while there was an increase of tertiary expenditure ($\mu = 9.32\%$) in the laggards.

Finally, if we compare laggards with the nonadopters, we see that there was more increase in the percentage growth in 'Tax revenue as % of GDP (var 1)', lesser decrease in the youth population of 20 to 24 years of age (var 5), more increase in the gross tertiary enrolment (var 6) and tertiary enrolment rate (var 7) in the nonadopters than the laggards. However, there was an increase ($\mu = 9.32\%$) in the 'tertiary expenditure as a percentage of governmental expenditure on education (var 8)' in the laggards while this expenditure was reduced ($\mu = -0.36\%$) in the nonadopters.

As we have identified some trends across the groups, it worth mentioning here that these groups were heterogeneous. For instance, each group was comprised of big as well as small countries.

Laggards-2000 Scenario:

In this section, we have analyzed what were 'laggards' like in terms of our study variables in the year 2000. Were they more or less at risk of adopting the PBF model in 2000? To answer these questions, we see the trend of GDP growth rate (var 2), given in Figure 9, and the percentage growths in variables 1, 5, 6, 7, and 8, given in Table 8 and illustrated in Figure 10. We see that in the year 2000, the laggards had a higher percentage growth in 'Tax revenue as % of GDP (var 1)' ($\mu = 6.76\%$), lesser decrease in the 'youth population of 20 to 24 years of age (var 5)' ($\mu = -0.26\%$), more increase in the 'gross tertiary enrolment rate (var 6)' ($\mu = 57.96\%$), more increase in the 'tertiary enrolment rate (var 7)' ($\mu = 59.2\%$), and a higher 'tertiary expenditure as a percentage of governmental expenditure on education (var 8)' ($\mu = 12.12\%$) than in 2012 and onwards. In the following paragraphs, we investigate these countries individually.

The Netherland seemed more at risk of adopting the PBF model in 2012. Although its tax rate (var 1) had substantially decreased in 2012, comparing to the situation in 2000, its 'youth of age 20 to 24 years' (var 5) was increasing, and consequently, its gross tertiary enrolment (var 6) and tertiary enrolment rate (var 7) had substantially increased in 2012.

Compared to the situation in 2013, Ireland had very high growth in tertiary enrolment rate (var 7) and tertiary expenditure (var 8) in 2000, but its economy was also in very good condition in 2000. In 2013, although expansion in tertiary enrolment rate continued with a simultaneous decrease in tertiary expenditure, the economy was then in bad condition.

Compared to the situation in 2012, Romania had very high growth in youth population of 20 to 24 years (var 5), gross tertiary enrolment (var 6), tertiary enrolment rate(var 7), and tertiary expenditure (var 8) in 2000. Nevertheless, Romania did not adopt the PBF model in 2000.

Bulgaria was experiencing declining economic growth (var 2), more growth in the tax rate(var 1), youth population of 20 to 24 years(var 5), tertiary enrolment(var 6), and tertiary enrolment rate(var 7) in 2000 with a simultaneous decrease in tertiary expenditure (var 8). However, it adopted the PBF model in 2015 when its economy was recovering, the tax rate had gone down, but its tertiary expenditure (var 8) was increasing.

Although Latvia witnessed more growth in tertiary enrolment (var 6), tertiary enrolment rate(var 7), and tertiary expenditure (var 8) in 2000, it adopted the PBF model in 2015 when its tertiary expenditure(var 8) and tax rate(var 1) had increased more.

Estonia seems to adopt the PBF model in 2017 when the growth in its gross tertiary enrolment and tertiary enrolment rate had abated, but its tax rate and tertiary expenditure had increased substantially.

Finally, Greece also seems similar to Estonia, but its tertiary expenditure data were not available. Therefore, it is difficult to say anything about it.

Thus, some countries could be at more risk of adopting the PBF model in 2000 if the variables which we have identified in this study play a significant role in the adoption and diffusion of the PBF model in higher education.

Figure 9: GDP Growth rate (annual %) of laggards in the year 2000

Figure 10: Laggards in 2000

Table 8: A hypothetical scnerio of the laggards in 2000. Percentage growth in five variables ('tax revenue (% of GDP)', '20-to-24 years population/100K total population', 'gross tertiary level enrollment', 'tertiary education participation rate(% of relevant age group)', and 'percentage of tertiary education expenditure (as % of total educational expenditure)' in the "laggards" during the last six years which include the year PBF model was adopted (t) and five years preceding it (t-5).

Laggards	tax_to_gdp_1	tax_to_gdp_1	% Δ	pop_20to24_5	pop_20to24_5	% Δ	tert_enrol	tert_enrol	% Δ	tert_enr	tert_enr	% Δ	tert_exp_	tert_exp_	% Δ
	@	@		@	@		@	@		@	@		@	@	
	t-5	t	t-5 to t	t-5	t	t-5 to t	t-5	t	t-5 to t	t-5	t	t-5 to t	t-5	t	t-5 to t
	Variable 1			Variable 5			Variable 6			Variable 7			Variable 8		
Netherland	20.87	20.94	0.32	7,197	6,024	-16.30	528,086	501,563	-5.02	47.47	52.28	10.15	30.12	28.89	-4.07
Croatia	22.75	22.27	-2.13	6,660	6,615	-0.68	80,723	95,706	18.56	26.24	32.38	23.43			
Romania	17.40	17.96	3.22	8,061	8,701	7.94	244,818	467,221	90.84	13.39	23.93	78.71	16.82	23.91	42.12
Ireland	26.50	26.38	-0.45	8,047	8,196	1.85	104,464	154,214	47.62	35.97	49.45	37.47	23.27	30.27	30.08
Bulgaria	12.33	17.16	39.11	7,193	7,619	5.92	220,100	274,695	24.81	36.40	44.13	21.23	18.16	14.36	-20.91
Latvia	19.41	20.78	7.08	6,930	6,795	-1.95	39,206	90,477	130.77	22.77	56.24	147.05	12.45	16.26	30.61
Estonia	22.87	19.66	-14.02	6,862	7,027	2.41	25,087	53,543	113.43	25.45	54.54	114.32	17.67	16.77	-5.12
Greece	18.58	22.47	20.93	7,862	7,761	-1.28	298,560	425,903	42.65	35.96	50.78	41.24		24.03	
Mean			6.76			-0.26				57.96		59.20			12.12

Conclusions

This paper aimed to develop a conceptual framework that can explain the adoption and diffusion of performance-based funding models in various European systems over the past 30 years, taking into account the peculiarities of European higher education systems. To achieve our objective, we tried to answer the question: what are the characteristics of European countries/provinces/states that have adopted performance funding over the past 30 years? Answering this question is essential because the most commonly stated determinants for the adoption and diffusion of the PBF model in Europe are not sufficient. While the spread of New Public Management and other movements no doubt are associated enthusiasm for PBF, these movements do not fully explain the phenomenon in the diverse set of European tertiary education systems. Therefore, to address conceptual and methodological limitations in previous studies and to better understand the phenomenon, we intend to conduct a quantitative study which may be guided by a robust conceptual framework. As a stepping-stone, we proposed here a conceptual framework for the adoption and diffusion of PBF in European higher education. This framework encompasses most of the institutional, national, and supranational actors and the varied contexts in which these actors coordinate.

To collect the preliminary evidence for the proposed conceptual framework, we conducted a descriptive study based on a limited set of economic, demographic, and educational variables. However, our findings are mixed because there is no clear trend or characteristic which can be associated with the adopters or nonadopters of the PBF model in Europe. While we hypothesized that the population size and growth in a country could be associated with the adoption of accountability policies in higher education, our analysis suggests that it is no more important in European higher education because not only big countries but also some small countries, such as Latvia and Estonia, have adopted the PBF model.

Nevertheless, our study does suggest that in most countries, expansion in gross tertiary enrollment, tertiary education enrolment rate, and tertiary expenditure are associated with the adoption of the PBF model. However, these variables do not fully explain the behavior of a country in terms of the adoption of the PBF model. Therefore, we need to expand the list of variables that may affect the behavior of the countries, including the country's relevant bureaucracy's analytical capacity and the country's political ideologies. Moreover, we intend to use some robust statistical techniques, such as event history analysis (EHA). Scholars in the US have used the EHA technique to study the adoption and diffusion of policy innovation, such as tax innovation, lottery adoption, and performance-based funding model, in various US states (Berry & Berry, 1990, 1992; McLendon et al., 2006). EHA can be used for longitudinal processes in higher education. While longitudinal processes can be studied using conventional statistical techniques, these techniques are not designed for studying longitudinal processes and often make assumptions that are sometimes violated in longitudinal processes. Also, cross-sectional data, which are generally used in static regression techniques, do not explain how temporal changes in the independent variables affect a dependent variable or in the outcome of interest. However, EHA has not been used very frequently in higher education due to various factors, for instance, the unavailability of longitudinal data. So, we hope that through EHA, we will be able to understand better the adoption of accountability in European higher education, including the PBF model.

While most European scholars have focused on the impact of the PBF model and have attributed the adoption of the PBF model to the spread of New Public Management (NPM), investigating the origins of the PBF model through policy adoption and diffusion lens and using robust statistical techniques is also essential.

References

- Arimoto, A., Teichler, U., & Cummings, W. (2013). *The changing academic profession: Major findings of a comparative survey*: Dordrecht: Springer. Google Scholar.
- Berry, F. S., & Berry, W. D. (1990). State lottery adoptions as policy innovations: An event history analysis. *American political science review*, 84(2), 395-415.
- Berry, F. S., & Berry, W. D. (1992). Tax innovation in the states: Capitalizing on political opportunity. *American Journal of Political Science*, 715-742.
- BFUG Secretariat. (2019). European Higher Education Area and Bologna Process. Retrieved from <http://www.ehea.info/index.php>
- Boer, H. d., Jongbloed, B., Bennenworth, P., Cremonini, L., Kolster, R., Kottmann, A., Lemmens-Krug, K., & Vossensteyn, H. (2015). *Performance-based funding and performance agreements in fourteen higher education systems: Report for the Ministry of Education, Culture and Science*. Retrieved from Enschede, the Netherland:
- Brennan, J. (2010). Burton Clark's The Higher Education System: Academic Organization in Cross-National Perspective. *London Review of education*, 8(3), 229-237.
- Brine, J. (2006). Lifelong learning and the knowledge economy: those that know and those that do not—the discourse of the European Union. *British Educational Research Journal*, 32(5), 649-665. doi:10.1080/01411920600895676
- Broucker, B., De Wit, K., & Leisyte, L. (2016). Higher education reform: a systematic comparison of ten countries from a new public management perspective *Positioning higher education institutions* (pp. 19-40): Brill Sense.
- Capano, G. (2011). Government continues to do its job. A comparative study of governance shifts in the higher education sector. *Public Administration*, 89(4), 1622-1642.
- Claeys-Kulik, A.-L., & Eastermann, T. (2015). *Define Thematic Report: Performance-based funding of Universities in Europe*. Retrieved from
- Clark, B. R. (1983). *The higher education system: Academic organization in cross-national perspective*. California: Univ of California Press.
- Clark, B. R. (1998). *Creating entrepreneurial universities: organizational pathways of transformation*. *Issues in Higher Education*: ERIC.
- de Boer, H. F. (2019). Higher education accountability: Book review of Robert Kelchen's Higher Education Accountability. *Higher education quarterly*, 73(3), 394-398.
- De Boer, H. F., Enders, J., & Schimank, U. (2008). Comparing higher education governance systems in four European countries *Governance and performance of education systems* (pp. 35-54): Springer.
- DiMaggio, P. J., & Powell, W. W. (1983). The iron cage revisited: Institutional isomorphism and collective rationality in organizational fields. *American Sociological Review*, 48(2), 147-160.
- European Commission. (2011a). *COMMUNICATION FROM THE COMMISSION TO THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT, THE COUNCIL, THE ECONOMIC AND SOCIAL COMMITTEE AND THE COMMITTEE OF THE REGIONS: Single Market Act - Twelve levers to boost growth and strengthen confidence - "Working together to create new growth"* (COM(2011) 206 final). Brussels Retrieved from <https://ec.europa.eu/transparency/regdoc/rep/1/2011/EN/1-2011-206-EN-F1-1.Pdf>.
- European Commission. (2011b). *COMMUNICATION FROM THE COMMISSION TO THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT, THE COUNCIL, THE EUROPEAN ECONOMIC AND SOCIAL COMMITTEE AND THE COMMITTEE OF THE REGIONS Supporting growth and jobs – an agenda for the modernisation of Europe's higher education systems*. (COM/2011/0567 final). Brussels.
- European Commission. (2012). *A Reinforced European Research Area Partnership for Excellence and Growth*. (COM(2012) 392 final 17.7.2012). Brussels.
- European Commission. (2015). *Horizon 2020:First Results*. Retrieved from Brussels:

- European Commission. (2018a). 2018 Ageing Report: Policy challenges for ageing societies. Retrieved from https://ec.europa.eu/info/news/economy-finance/policy-implications-ageing-examined-new-report-2018-may-25_en
- European Commission. (2018b). *National Student Fee and Support Systems in European Higher Education 2018/19 Eurydice – Facts and Figures*. Retrieved from Luxembourg:
- Frølich, N. (2008). *The politics of steering by numbers: Debating performance-based funding in Europe*. Retrieved from Oslo, Norway: www.nifustep.no
- Frølich, N., Kalpazidou Schmidt, E., & Rosa, M. J. (2010). Funding systems for higher education and their impacts on institutional strategies and academia: A comparative perspective. *International Journal of Educational Management*, 24(1), 7-21.
- Gornitzka, Å. (2006). *The open method of coordination as practice: A watershed in European education policy?* Retrieved from Oslo:
- Hearn, J. C., McLendon, M. K., & Linthicum, K. C. (2017). Conceptualizing State Policy Adoption and Diffusion. In M. B. Paulsen (Ed.), *Higher Education: Handbook of Theory and Research: Published under the Sponsorship of the Association for Institutional Research (AIR) and the Association for the Study of Higher Education (ASHE)* (pp. 309-354). Cham: Springer International Publishing.
- Hearn, J. C., McLendon, M. K., & Linthicum, K. C. (2017). Conceptualizing state policy adoption and diffusion *Higher education: Handbook of theory and research* (pp. 309-354): Springer.
- Hearn, J. C., & Ness, E. C. (2017). The ecology of state higher-education policymaking in the US *Towards the Private Funding of Higher Education* (pp. 19-47): Routledge.
- Huisman, J., & Currie, J. (2004). Accountability in higher education: Bridge over troubled water? *Higher Education*, 48(4), 529-551. doi:10.1023/B:HIGH.0000046725.16936.4c
- Johnstone, D. B., & Marcucci, P. N. (2010). *Financing Higher Education Worldwide: Who Pays? Who Should Pay?* : Johns Hopkins University Press.
- Jongbloed, B., Kaiser, F., van Vught, F., & Westerheijden, D. F. (2018). Performance Agreements in Higher Education: A New Approach to Higher Education Funding. In A. Curaj, L. Deca, & R. Pricopie (Eds.), *European Higher Education Area: The Impact of Past and Future Policies* (pp. 671-687). Cham: Springer International Publishing.
- Jongbloed, B., & Vossensteyn, H. (2001). Keeping up performances: An international survey of performance-based funding in higher education. *Journal of Higher Education Policy and Management*, 23(2), 127-145.
- Kelchen, R. (2018). *Higher Education Accountability*: Johns Hopkins University Press.
- Kivistö, J., & Kohtamäki, V. (2016). Does Performance-Based Funding Work? *Positioning Higher Education Institutions* (pp. 215-226): Springer.
- McLendon, M. K., & Hearn, J. C. (2013). The resurgent interest in performance-based funding for higher education. *Academe*, 99(6), 25-30.
- McLendon, M. K., Hearn, J. C., & Deaton, R. (2006). Called to account: Analyzing the origins and spread of state performance-accountability policies for higher education. *Educational Evaluation and Policy Analysis*, 28(1), 1-24.
- Orr, D. (2010). Integrating an Aging Student Population into Higher Education--Challenges for Evidence-Based Policy in Europe. *Canadian Journal of Higher Education*, 40(3), 25-42.
- Radaelli, C. M. (2003). *The Open Method of Coordination: A new governance architecture for the European Union?* Retrieved from Stockholm: file:///C:/Users/ijaza/OneDrive%20-%20University%20of%20Georgia/IHE/Research%20Assistantship/The%20Open%20Method%20of%20Coordination-a%20new%20governance%20architecture%20for%20the%20European%20Union.pdf
- Shahjahan, R. A. (2012). The roles of international organizations (IOs) in globalizing higher education policy. In J. C. Smart & M. B. Paulsen (Eds.), *Higher education: Handbook of Theory and Research* (pp. 369-407): Springer Netherlands.

- Shahjahan, R. A., & Kezar, A. J. (2013). Beyond the "National Container": Addressing Methodological Nationalism in Higher Education Research. *Educational Researcher*, 42(1), 20-29. doi:10.3102/0013189x12463050
- Slaughter, S., & Rhoades, G. (2004). *Academic capitalism and the new economy: Markets, state, and higher education*: JHU Press.
- Vaira, M. (2004). Globalization and higher education organizational change: A framework for analysis. *Higher education*, 48(4), 483-510.
- Veiga, A., & Amaral, A. (2006). The open method of coordination and the implementation of the Bologna process. *Tertiary Education and Management*, 12(4), 283-295. doi:10.1080/13583883.2006.9967174
- Weible, C. M., & Sabatier, P. A. (2018). *Theories of the Policy Process*: Taylor & Francis.